

 Database

Not shared: draw a card
Max 1 article/researcher

Shared: max 2 articles
per researcher

Fame: 3

 Database

Not shared: draw a card
Max 1 article/researcher

Shared: max 2 articles
per researcher

Fame: 3

 Database

Not shared: draw a card
Max 1 article/researcher

FALSE

If Review: -6 Fame for you
-2 Fame for each article

Fame: 3

 Experiment

Not shared: draw a card
Max 1 article/researcher

Shared: max 2 articles
per researcher

Fame: 2

 Experiment

Not shared: draw a card
Max 1 article/researcher

Shared: max 2 articles
per researcher

Fame: 2

 Experiment

Not shared: draw a card
Max 1 article/researcher

FALSE

If Review: -4 Fame for you
-2 Fame for each article

Fame: 2

 Code

Not shared: draw a card
Max 1 article/researcher

Shared: max 2 articles
per researcher

Fame: 1

 Code

Not shared: draw a card
Max 1 article/researcher

Shared: max 2 articles
per researcher

Fame: 1

 Code

Not shared: draw a card
Max 1 article/researcher

FALSE

If Review: -2 Fame for you
-1 Fame for each article

Fame: 1